

iImagine

Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Updated Plan

iImagine Deliverable D2.4

30/04/2024

Abstract

This deliverable provides an update to the previous deliverable offering an overview on how project results, developments and branding will be communicated. Moreover, a plan for the engagement with the targeted audiences, a dissemination strategy, the description of promotion, outreach, training, and co-design activities are presented in the document along with a dissemination plan.

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D2.4 Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Updated Plan

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Introduction

The iImagine project aims to deploy, operate, validate, and promote a dedicated iImagine AI framework and platform. The project also develops and delivers five operational and three prototype AI-based image analysis services with image repositories with open access for researchers' exploitation. The project also supports three additional use cases onboarded through a project open call that ran in 2023.

The services on which the use cases are working are currently in the development phase; they will be promoted to their respective users when they are operational on the iImagine AI platform during the second and third years of the project. Therefore, the following plan provides detailed initiatives for the project to continue to achieve this goal.

Structure of the document

- Results and achievements of the first reporting period
- An overview of the activities carried on during the previous period
- Target audiences and the targeted Engagement strategies
- Plans for M19–36

Purpose of the Dissemination, Communication and Engagement plan and the interim progress report

iImagine has the objective to deploy, operate, validate, and promote a dedicated iImagine AI framework and platform connected to EOSC and AI4EU, giving researchers in aquatic sciences open access to a diverse portfolio of AI-based image analysis services and image repositories from multiple RIs, working on and of relevance to the overarching theme of 'Healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters'.

Within the project, the main objectives of WP2 are to ensure that project results are captured, disseminated, and exploited for maximum impact, to manage both internal and external communication and dissemination, to liaise with stakeholders, and to organise project events and support participation at external events. T2.2 aligns closely with the activities in T2.1 (Innovation Management and Exploitation) as outlined in the D2.2 Innovation Management Plan¹ and D2.5 Innovation Management Progress Report (in preparation). As part of WP2 (Innovation Management and Communications), T2.2 (led by EGI.eu) deals with iImagine Communication, Dissemination and Engagement activities.

The project has identified eight Key Exploitable Results (KER), which are at the core of the DCE strategy:

¹ D2.2 First Innovation Management Plan, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7760155>

1. Marine litter assessment
2. Zooscan – Ecotaxa Pipeline
3. Marine Ecosystem Monitoring
4. Oil Spill Detection
5. Flowcam Plankton Identification
6. Prototype Imaging Services
7. The iMagine AI Platform
8. Best practices

The core activities of T2.2 focus on disseminating these KERs to the various target audiences. For this purpose, the activities are mapped to the stakeholder analysis.

This deliverable updates D2.1², in which the overall plan for these activities was laid out, mapped to target audiences, set against a timeline, and matched with suitable indicators for success. T2.2 worked on an overall plan to provide indications on how project results, developments, and branding will be communicated, how iMagine intends to engage with stakeholders, a clear dissemination strategy, and the description of promotion, consultancy, outreach, training, and co-design activities, in addition to a dissemination plan to be updated in the next deliverable release. This deliverable also reports on the period M1–M18 and will lay out the plans for M19–M36 (which will be reported in the final T2.2 deliverable D2.5).

The objectives of the iMagine DCE plan are three-fold:

- Increase Awareness: Raise awareness about the iMagine project and its services among all the relevant target audiences in the aquatic science community.
- User Acquisition: Attract the users of the services to engage with iMagine.
- Collaboration: Foster partnerships and collaborations with relevant organisations and research institutes.

Overview of the activities

After creating the brand identity, T2.2 took care of the website's launch, content creation, and continuous maintenance. Both brand identity and website launch were achieved ahead of schedule in M3. The website includes (at M18) different sections featuring the project team and governance overview, the KERs, the use cases, available results (such as the iMagine AI Platform and Tips for AI processing) and links to project outputs (deliverables, presentations, publications).

² D2.1 First Communication, Dissemination and Engagement plan, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7462914>

Branding

At the start of the project, a large part of the iImagine visual identity i.e. the logo, branding elements and document/presentation templates, were developed quickly and distributed amongst partners via the Communications Toolkit (available for partners on Confluence) and the [Project Brandguide](#). Various promotional materials such as a calling card with the website QR code, a flyer, a sticker, a video animation, USB cables, sustainable goodies and a general use poster were also developed. For extended documentation about the iImagine branding, see [D2.1](#).

From M6 onwards, as the first project outputs were delivered, the communication tools and processes were fine-tuned. Partners have developed their posters, combining their branding with the project's (or supported by EGI as task leader if needed). The website is used as a channel to disseminate information about published deliverables (in the form of news items), and partners deliver presentations about their contributions to the project using the iImagine presentation template.

For the second half of the project, the project will create pintables to showcase the services and short videos showcasing each project KER.

Website

The project website, accessible at imagine-ai.eu, was set up immediately, allowing for quick communication of the project's essential information, such as contact details, team and governance, and overall project goals. The section about results and resources, lists, and links provides all publicly available deliverables, presentations, and any other materials created by project partners.

The plan for M19-M36 is to implement the service section, add the use cases onboarded with the open call iterations, and increase the number of news items about these elements.

Figure 1 - Website visits

The website analytics show that the most visited pages are the use case pages overall, the page about the iImagine AI Platform, and the call for use cases.

Social media

The project's [LinkedIn page](#), which has over 100 followers, has shown a consistent engagement rating of 5.5% and 7.5%, aligning with similar pages' results (such as [Blue-Cloud 2026](#)). Special attention has been paid to creating posts for events where the

project was showcased. In the period M19–M36, an effort will be put into creating 'LinkedIn-friendly' visuals such as 'carrousels' to increase engagement for complex content (e.g. the use cases and the related services). As the project progresses, partners will be encouraged to become habitual in tagging iMagine on LinkedIn for their project-related posts.

X/Twitter remains active but with less investment due to the instability of the social media channel.

Events

Exhibition Booths and Events

From the start, iMagine has been present at every event booth hosted by the project coordinator – EGI. M1–M12 focused on awareness raising. Assisted by a striking branding that stands out, the project dissemination materials attracted attention and instigated many conversations at the respective booths. Working in collaboration with the other EGI coordinated projects (such as [interTwin](#) and [EGI-ACE](#)) has allowed iMagine to reach audiences that are not necessarily familiar with the concept of aquatic science and technology applied to it (such as [EOSC Symposium](#)), or with secondary target audiences (such as businesses during [Data Spaces Symposium](#)).

While M1–12 mainly focused on setting up the basic channels and tools, from M13 onwards, the strategy shifted towards differentiation and participation in more domain-specific events. These include the [IMDIS conference](#) and [EGU](#) (environmental sciences), where iMagine co-hosted an exhibition booth in M19 and where more activities are planned for Y3. An internal workshop with the use cases has also presented additional events where the project could find dissemination venues in Y3.

Project presentations

Partners reported 15 events at which iMagine was presented once or multiple times. The presentations and respective events are listed on the [project's website](#).

Additionally, excluding the visitors at the exhibitions and the participation in larger events (such as EGU23, ISC23 and EGU24, where the potential attendees number spans from 2,500 to 20,000 participants), self-reporting from the partners let us estimate a reach of over 880 attendees.

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Figure 2 – Igor Atake presenting the first outcomes of UC4 at EGU24

Internal workshops

iImagine hosted the following internal workshops and meetings in the first half of the project:

Table 1 – Project Internal workshops

Date	Topic	Link
14/09/2022	iImagine administrative kick-off meeting (online)	https://indico.egi.eu/event/5919/
22/09/2023	iImagine technical kick-off meeting	https://indico.egi.eu/event/5920/
30-31/01/2023	iImagine First Competence Centre workshop	https://indico.egi.eu/event/5999/
29/09/2023	Use case Dissemination and Communication Support	https://app.mural.co/t/egi3550/m/egi3550/1695966032458/dd143e781759c7c8b897d667355a638fca3fa6cb?sender=u297868c2869ea72cbfe74783

11/10/2023	iMagine General Assembly and Project Management Board	https://indico.egi.eu/event/6264/
19–20/03/2024	iMagine Second Competence Centre Workshop	https://indico.egi.eu/event/6371/

Webinars

The project hosted a webinar on the AI platform for its users on 15/12/2022. For M19–36, T2.2 plans to organise additional webinars with mature use cases and AI experts. In addition to the above, T2.2 organised FITSM training during the EGI2023 Conference. Additional training is foreseen for Y3, allowing all service owners to deliver their services effectively.

Zenodo

Since its beginning, the project has established a community on Zenodo to showcase iMagine outputs. T2.2 helps the collection and deposit process of the presentations given by partners. Deliverables are also collected in the community. Overall, all documents available in the Zenodo community have received over 920 downloads.

In March 2024, iMagine was selected to **participate** in the pilot of the **HORIZON-ZEN project**. As iMagine has started using Zenodo as the repository for all training datasets produced by the project's use cases, being part of this pilot project will allow iMagine customising all metadata fields to best match the aquatic science community's needs. This way, all datasets already available on SEANOE, the open scientific data repository in the marine sciences field, could be cross-referenced on Zenodo for more completeness.

In addition to Zenodo, relevant datasets have been submitted for consideration to the **Global Climate Observing System's Essential Climate Variables**. Moreover, iMagine deliverables on best practices are under evaluation for inclusion in the **Ocean Best Practices** repository.

Summary of dissemination outputs

Table 2 offers a review of planned T2.2 activities, as described in D2.1, during M1–M18.

Table 2 – Overview of the dissemination outputs

Description	Delivered	Comment
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Website	✓	Website published and regularly updated, see Website
Communications toolkit	✓	M3, continuously updated
Social media accounts	✓	LinkedIn published and regularly updated, see Social Media
Kick-off meeting	✓	Organised at EGI22, see Internal Workshops
Event participation	✓	Partners presented iMagine at 15 events, project present at 5 exhibition booths
Repository for publications	✓	See Zenodo
Project Branding	✓	Branding guide delivered
Dissemination, Communication and Engagement Plan	✓	Delivered with D2.1 in M5
Visual Materials	✓	See D2.1
Support in event organisation	✓	Support to the organisation of the First and Second Competence Centre Workshops (M4.2, M4.4)

Not planned activities:

- Launch of the project [Open Call for Use Cases](#), two iterations, three use cases selected.

KPIs for communication and dissemination

Table 3 – Status of KPIs at M18

Measure description	M18 status	Comments
# Page visits	~500 per month	Steady number of visits to the website since October 2022 with

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		peaks around the open call campaigns and events
# engagement rate on social media	4%	average
#deliverable views and downloads (Zenodo)	921 downloads 1,051 views	
News items	24 news items	
# Clicks on project-related content in the EGI newsletter	Avg 4.2%	The open call news was published twice in the EGI newsletter, receiving around 500 clicks (note that the EGI newsletter has over 3,200 subscribers)
# attendees during presentations at events	Over 880 participants	The number doesn't consider the participation in larger events such as EGU23 and ISC23 conferences, where the potential attendees to the presentations are over 2500 participants
Use Cases	11 use cases	The open call helped to onboard 3 new use cases
Visual Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The project logo in different variations - The project colours and instructions on how to use them - A moo cards - A sticker - Roll-up banner and variations - Project posters variations - Zoom backgrounds - Social media banners 	All visual materials are available to partners from the Communications Toolkit on Confluence. Moreover, EGI has helped partners customise the templates for specific partner events.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Document templates - A general presentation of the project 	
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Rather than focusing on absolute numbers for reporting social media activities, the project is basing its social media ‘successes’ on two parameters: regularity (all relevant content advertised) and audience engagement rate (benchmarked against other, similar accounts).

Collaborations and partnerships

EOSC Landscape

Following the recommendations from the project review and leveraging the connections in place thanks to the project partners, iImagine has strengthened its relationship with AI and aquatic science-related projects to make the most out of the collaboration with them. In particular, the project collaborated with AI4EOSC and AI4Europe (now AIoD) in the organisation of AI and ML sessions during the EGI2022 and EGI2023 conferences. iImagine use cases have also been showcased in the webinar series organised by [ANERIS](#) and [AI4EOSC](#).

Aquatic and Environmental projects and RIs

Moreover, the project established a stronger partnership with Blue-Cloud 2026, together with which it organised the satellite event [“The Data We Need for the Ocean We Care For”](#) during the Ocean Decade Conference 2024 and will participate in the EU Maritime Day with a workshop on [“Observations to knowledge: Unlocking Ocean Insights”](#).

Last but not least, the project has collaborated with several environmental landscape projects by participating in an ENVRI cross-collaboration network started by the newly launched ENVRI-Hub NEXT. These projects are IRISCC, ENVRI-Hub NEXT, ENVRINNOV, and Blue-Cloud, and the network has expanded to an additional 10 projects³.

A session on unlocking the potential of environmental data is planned at EGI2024.

Identified challenges

Identifying the appropriate press outlets to inform about the project has been challenging. However, with the collaboration of Blue-Cloud 2026, the project will embed the technology and use cases of iImagine into a larger context. T2.2 will closely work with the partners to increase their involvement in creating compelling stories about the use cases.

³ These are AMRIT, GROOM-RI, eLTER, PHENET, LandSeaLot, AQUARIUS, LifeWatch ERIC, MINKE, EVERSE

The partners will also be encouraged to share these stories within their networks, including press outlets. The project will try to identify suitable outlets like Horizon Europe Magazine to promote the project outcomes.

Engagement

Target Audiences

The project's target audiences have been initially identified in the Description of the Action and then further detailed in D2.1. Based on a workshop with the use cases and the project objectives, we conducted a further analysis to identify the target audiences we should focus on to ensure iMagine has a stronger impact in M19-M36.

The analysis, aided by the Stakeholder Engagement Assessment Matrix (SEAM) detailed in D2.2 and D2.5, identifies the stakeholders to prioritise based on the assumption that the project will not be able to meet the needs of all stakeholders simultaneously. The prioritisation exercise helps get engagement started. 'Users' and 'Similar AI initiatives' were identified as the key stakeholders towards whom engagement activities had to be targeted.

Most of the use cases also identify researchers as their users as the main target audience of their developed or to-be-developed services.

Stakeholder Group	Unaware of the project	Aware of the project			
		Resistant	Neutral	Supportive	Actively Engaged
Users	C				D
Service and Content Providers			C		D
Infrastructure Providers			C		D
Similar AI initiatives	C			D	
Suppliers	C		D		
Organisations/Agencies from different disciplines			C	D	
Policy Makers				C	D
Decision Makers	C		D		
General Public			C D		

Figure 3 - SEAM further described in D2.5

Specific measures per target group

Users

To promote the project to Users, iMagine will focus on

- **Present the use cases and their services:** This way, potential users would understand the benefits of the developed services for them to use them in their own research activities.
- **Easy access:** Improving the project website will make it easier to find the services and will allow users to readily access the resources they are most interested in.

How to? The project will

- **Create videos and tutorials, organise webinars** to demonstrate the services to users, help them understand the value proposition and see how iImagine services fit their needs.
- **Highlight and emphasise the expertise** iImagine brings to the table to give the users confidence in the quality and reliability of your services.
- **Showcase success stories**, further promoting the use cases and using the KER ambassadors to demonstrate how to use the iImagine services to solve a research challenge.

Here are some of the key messages the project will use to promote the iImagine services and AI platform to users.

Benefits

- Automate tedious image analysis. Spend less time manually classifying marine life and focus on ground-breaking research. Our AI-powered image recognition tools analyse vast datasets in seconds, freeing you for in-depth analysis.
- Uncover hidden patterns: Go beyond what the human eye can see. Our ML algorithms detect subtle variations in aquatic imagery, revealing ecological relationships and population trends you might have missed.
- Answer complex ecological questions: Formulate specific queries about species abundance, distribution, or behaviour. Our image processing system extracts insights from massive image datasets, providing data-driven answers to your research questions.

Highlight the Expertise

- Our team combines cutting-edge AI expertise with a deep understanding of aquatic ecosystems. This ensures our image-processing tools are tailored to the specific needs of aquatic science research. – *with links to the most advanced use cases on a rotation.*
- We are committed to developing and refining our AI models. Our use cases constantly work alongside AI specialists to ensure the accuracy and reliability of our image analysis tools.
- Our support team comprises AI specialists and aquatic science experts, ensuring you will receive prompt feedback on any questions or technical issues related to the iImagine image processing tools.
- Discover the tips on image processing and analysis our experts have already compiled to ease your experience with the iImagine AI platform.

Showcase Success Stories

- OBSEA uses the iImagine AI platform to analyse underwater observatory footage, automating fish classification and expediting the research on species distribution in the Mediterranean Sea.
- The team at IMEV leveraged our AI and ML image recognition service to speed up the zooplankton recognition process, saving up to 1 hour per day on manual identification processes.

The use cases will help further strengthen and refine the messages and support their dissemination to the target audience.

Similar AI Initiatives

Thanks to its existing collaboration with AI4EOSC, iImagine can already foster some joint activities, such as the organisation of online workshops or presentations. However, this liaison should be reinforced and expanded to other initiatives on AI to improve iImagine's reach. By sharing success stories and testimonials from the use cases and the research achievements made possible by the services (e.g. timesaving because of the use of the iImagine AI platform), iImagine will be able to demonstrate the positive impact the project has on research.

Ideally, iImagine could focus on the following activities:

- Identify the relevant AI initiatives to contact
- Keep on organising joint initiatives
- Present the services and offer collaboration opportunities

Identifying relevant AI initiatives should involve two simultaneous steps. First, scope the consortium to find useful links and contacts; second, use CORDIS, the European Commission database, to look for projects with similar objectives (i.e., the development of AI and ML services, irrespective of the domain). The contacts gathered with this exercise will be addressed with at least two mailings – using the EGI newsletter platform – informing the recipients about the project and the opportunities available for them. The mailing will help disseminating the iImagine use cases and their services, calling other AI and ML initiatives to, for example, widening the pool of available tools on the iImagine AI Platform or improving current models based on other initiatives' experiences. Moreover, bits of advice on protocols and standardisation could also be sought. In addition, the option to participate in joint webinars or conference sessions could also be appealing. The mailing will be aided by communication on LinkedIn, exploring the opportunity for paid campaigns with specific messages, including but not limited to:

We believe in the power of collaboration to accelerate progress in AI-powered aquatic image processing. Let's explore potential areas where our projects can work together.

- iImagine is committed to open communication and knowledge exchange. How can we collaborate to organise workshops or online forums to share best practices and advance the field?
- Imagine the impact of combining our projects' expertise! Let's discuss potential joint publications or presentations to showcase the power of AI in aquatic science.

- We view your project as a valuable source of inspiration. Together, let's push the boundaries of AI-powered image processing in aquatic science through healthy competition.

Combining these strategies to approach the target groups should successfully shift Users and Similar AI initiatives from being unaware of iImagine to being aware, supportive, and engaged.

Plan M19–M36

M19–36 will involve intensifying existing measures, with continuous promotion and publication of project outputs and deliverables. The ongoing promotion of the deliverables and use cases will continue, including creating print materials and webinars focused on the use cases and their services.

The webinars will demonstrate the services, enabling interested users to request access to the platform and use it for training their datasets. During the final stage of the project, a dedicated campaign will showcase the project KERs to demonstrate the impact of iImagine. This campaign will include videos, news items, and stories published on our website and distributed via partners towards partner's websites and outlets, press contacts, and event presentations/posters.

An evaluation will be conducted to determine if and what aspects of the project outputs would benefit from a dedicated print publication. These could be a major hand-out at the closing event and serve for post-project dissemination. Finally, iImagine will increase its presence at various events through booths and presentations. Partners will continue to submit abstracts for events in M18–M36, and T2.2 will work closely with colleagues in the EGI communication team to streamline event booth participation in as many events as feasible within the budget. Event plans for the future are recorded on Confluence to allow for proper coordination.

Planned events for the second half of the project include:

EGU24: at the time of writing, a very successful event participation was conducted at EGU24. Two posters about the project were presented and iImagine was prominently featured at the EGI booth. This will be repeated in EGU25 with a larger shared booth and a more prominent presence in the programme, e.g. using the opportunity of a training session or a town hall meeting.

TNC24: iImagine will be present with a (shared) booth at this major multi-disciplinary conference.

EGI2024: iImagine will curate a public session on environmental data in the programme and will have a prominent place in the shared flagship event booth.

EU Maritime Day: iImagine will participate in the workshop **"Observations to knowledge: Unlocking Ocean Insights"** together with Blue-Cloud 2026 and EuroGOOS.

IMDIS 2024: iImagine sponsors the 2024 edition of the International Conference on Marine Data and Information Systems. Posters and talks about the project will be featured during the conference.

EOSS Symposium: iImagine will be present at the EGI shared event booth.

Digital Ocean Forum; however, iMagine's participation in the 2024 edition of the event is not yet confirmed at the time of writing.

As suggested in the workshop with the use cases, the project will investigate additional dissemination opportunities more closely; these venues include the OCEANS conference, the MARTECH workshop, and SeaTechWeek.

Despite the project ending in August 2025, the closing event is planned for June 2025, co-located with EGI2025.

Annex

The Annex presents a few of the visuals created to promote the project.

Figure 4 – Project logo variations

Figure 5 – Examples of Open Call dissemination visuals

Figure 6 – Project Moo Card

Figure 7 –Project Leaflet

iImagine

iImagine, AI-supported imaging data and services for ocean and marine science

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Platform Architecture

Internal use cases

- Production environment
- R&D application prototypes

Researching the Research Infrastructures 5

EOSC AI4EU

Platform AI Platform Services: scalable platform for identifying and sharing AI/ML applications

Community serving:

- Internal use cases
- External use cases

AI4EU **EOSC**

Infrastructure

EGI **CSIC** **INCD** **IMIRIS** **WALTON**

- 1800 TeraBytes
- 132,000 CPU hours
- 6,000,000 GPU hours

4 National cloud infrastructures - OpenStack, OpenShift, Ceph, Storage - from Open Storage, Talos, Ceph

Pass by booth #101 to ask for more questions!

START: 01/08/2022 - END: 31/08/2025
 CONSORTIUM: 34 partners from Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain, Turkey
 12 connected RIs

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About iImagine

The primary goal of iImagine is to provide AI-driven application services for image analysis within aquatic sciences. These services cover segmentation and object recognition and are presently in the validation phase.

What is it for?

The iImagine AI Platform offers a suite of AI-powered image analysis tools for researchers in aquatic sciences, facilitating a better understanding of the scientific phenomena and applying AI and ML for processing image data.

What does it do?

The Platform supports the entire machine learning cycle leveraging data from underwater platforms, satellites, microscopes, drones, and satellites, and utilizing distributed resources across Europe. It enables easy sharing and deployment of AI models.

Use Cases

iImagine has 8 use cases addressing marine and freshwater research and its technical implementation in different maturity stages. 3 additional use cases were selected through a project open call in 2023.

Available Datasets and Models

Several training datasets are available on Zenodo (search for "iImagine project" community). iImagine is part of the HORIZON-2021 pilot to introduce ad-hoc metadata for dataset description.

The use cases experimented with several training models and annotation tools, including but not limited to:

- YOLO
- Labelbox
- Roboflow Annotation
- FAISS-B-CNN
- CVAT

Discover iImagine | Read the abstract

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Figure 8 –One of the posters prepared for iImagine